

Business model on Inventory Management Performance of Super Markets with Moderating Role of Demand Uncertainty: A case of Oman and Pakistan major organizations

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ABSTRACT: The revolutionizing of supply chain dynamics has taken place through merging information management systems with inventory control, leading to enhanced predictability and faster flow of information which makes it possible for the stock-outs to be avoided. This research paper investigates the intrinsic connection between IT system efficacy and inventory management skills, and thus provides useful information to inventory managers who aim at enhancing supply chain efficiency in fluctuating demand situations. A total of 208 responses were collected using a 5-likert scale questionnaire from different supermarket in Oman and Pakistan from supply chain managers and supervisors through non-probabilistic sampling techniques. Analysis was conducted using SPSS version 29.0 which showed that Vendor managed inventory (VMI), material requirement planning (MRP) systems and warehousing management systems (WMS) had positive direct correlation with IM performance significantly. This study emphasizes that understanding IT system foundations in regard to managing inventory is essential when there is no certainty about future market fluctuations. Supermarkets can take advantage of these implications by comprehensively investigating their IT framework for improvement areas. Supermarkets that respond appropriately to changes in customers' requirements also reduce costs and bottlenecks thereby increasing satisfaction among customers.

Keywords: Information Management Systems, Inventory Management Performance, Supermarket, Demand Uncertainty, Vendor Managed Inventory system, Warehouse Management System.

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1. Introduction

In today's dynamic market environment, rapid changes in market trends necessitate companies to establish efficient and adaptable inventory management capable of responding to customers' uncertain demands. Uncertainty in demand stems from various sources, and its impact can manifest as either short-term or long-term uncertainties, depending on the speed of its effects. In the swift advancements of information technology and highly globalized business environments driven by stiff competition, supply chain planning has become one of the most important practices for both manufacturing and services-oriented companies. Inventory management is crucial to any business operation and forms the spine of supply chain management (SCM). An example of an important inventory management decision is maintaining enough counts in warehouse for each item (Alam, M.K., 2024).

The advent of technology and widespread availability of software with process-driven applications have revolutionized inventory management. Today's businesses operate more complex and longer supply chains with high stakeholder expectations (Kapitonov, I.A. et al., 2017). On the other hand, businesses are nowadays striving to meet varied consumer needs through SCM as well as managing emerging issues like shorter product lives and changing customer tastes (Emrouznejad et al., 2023). Efficient collaboration between related firms is vital for successful supply chains (Huang et al., 2018). This cooperation is facilitated by information systems that quicken processes while ensuring error-free files. In this case, it can be said that optimization of supply chain nodes is not only a duty within one department but requires collective efforts from all stakeholders across the entire supply chain. These sub-variables include vendor-managed inventory system; materials resource planning system; warehouse management system (MRP). A good example includes supplier managed inventories whereby suppliers forecast customers demand using their knowledge regarding consumers' behavior (Rika, G.R. et al., 2020).

These integrated factors bring in the idea of total score for managing stock which incorporates objectives like cost minimization and profit maximization as well as customer satisfaction Montasser., H.H.M.& El-Nakeeb (2017). Nevertheless, there is a key challenge in relation to demand uncertainty in inventories due to the fact that it can be difficult to forecast or manage changes in consumption levels. However, records are kept, and history and current situations are measured so that movement from one demand state to another could be anticipated hence controlling this risk characteristic of modern supply chain management techniques (Navi R., 2003; Kou-manakos D.P., 2008).

This study aims at improving supermarket inventory performance by making them responsive to unanticipated consumer demands directly linked with end-users particularly within localities like Oman and Pakistan. This study seeks to fill this gap with regards to inventory management practices in big supermarkets in Oman and Pakistan, with special attention to the moderating role of demand uncertainty on inventory management performance.

While inventory management is a critical success factor in supermarkets there is still a scant literature on the business models that relate to this criterion in terms of its performance on inventory management with particular concern to the moderating role of

demand uncertainty. Earlier research shows that implemented specific business models improves the inventory performance by including strategies in forecast, demand planning, and risk management (Axsäter, 2006; Kouvelis et al., 2006). However, these models do not consider the different degrees of demand uncertainty in EMS as a complex issue as noted by Christopher and Peck (2004). This study to offer insights which can help to strengthen and optimize the business continuity of inventory to retail business in the considered countries, to do this it firstly presents a business model that features strategies for managing demand uncertainty. The contribution of this study will continue from the existing literature by discussing the moderate factor of demand uncertainty in the management of inventory in supermarkets, with which will develop a significant framework of supermarkets in similar emerging markets.

2. Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

Nowadays, corporations from various industries are highly dependent on information technology in e-commerce platforms with a vision of smooth operations and increased profits. Data mining is viewed as a key approach to facilitate accurate and timely decision making for businesses. The dominative influence of Information Technology has reshaped markets by closing gaps and meeting customer demands. Experts keep coming up with new software and hardware on a constant basis that are fitted into daily activities across the sectors (Ahmad, A. et al., 2021). Information technology has become an integral part of strategic planning for many different types of business organizations ranging from individual point-of-sale systems to complete company-wide structures (Venkatesh, Thong, & Xu, 2012). For example, customized software solutions such as Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) can be used by companies to handle their multifaceted needs that involve human resource management, supply chain logistics system accounting as well as customer relationship management. This chapter will delve into three different aspects of the IT: vendor-managed inventory systems; material requirement planning; warehouse management systems (Kodama, M. et al., 2012; Shannaq B.I Al Shamsi S Abdul Majeed 2019), thus emphasizing its essential role in present day's business strategies.

Vendor-Managed Inventory System and Inventory Management Performance

Efficient Vendor Management Inventory (VMI) systems use the information derived from warehouses or point-of-sale systems, analyze it and then take decisions in relation to stock replenishment. To enhance the practice of vendor-managed inventory, there has been an increase in retailer-vendor partnership agreements (Laudon K.C., & Laudon J.P., 2011). Furthermore, there is specialized Electronic Data Interchange software that can be used to expedite point-of-sale transactions. The idea of VMI has grown to cover other sectors apart from retailing (Achabal, McIntyre S.H., Smith, & Kalyanam, 2000; Chachon, & Fisher, 1997). Orobias et al. (2020) have established a strong relationship between Inventory Management (IM) and small business financial performance. However, despite this development, VMI still implies substantial sharing of information. Overall, replenishment decisions are likely to succeed when suppliers share their information concerning stock

levels, promotional activities, costs as well as anticipated demand with regard avoiding both side's sub-optimization.

Consequently, big data analytics in logistics and supply chain management will allow proactive suppliers can access necessary information early enough so as cut down on lead times according to Wang et al (Wang, G., Gunasekaran, Ngai, & Papadopoulos, 2016). Similarly streamlining the supply chain by eliminating echelons reduces delays in information and material flow thereby eliminating one source of decision-making distortion (Kaipia, R., Holmström, J., and Tanskanen, K., 2002). In a study about two stage supply chain, Yu et al found out that this integrated strategy involves one manufacturer and various customers (Wang, & Liang Liang, 2012). Notwithstanding the fact that items are manufactured and replenished just in time across all levels of this integrated supply chain, items are degraded at all these levels. On the other hand, Wu & Sarker explore a single vendor, a single retailer and an adjacent VMI warehouse chain with a freshness clause that significantly affects decisions of both parties (Wu, B., & Sarker, 2013). Ee Ma and colleagues (Ee Ma, Ying, D., Guan, & Huang, 2013) build a model to handle special sales offers which determines optimal quantities for shortages and orders when such sales are available for perishable products.

Wal-Mart is among large organizations like Proctor and Gamble who have adopted VMI systems; hence others should emulate their direction (Taleizadeh et al., 2013). This suggests that vendor-managed inventory has potential to improve the overall effectiveness of inventory management parts.

H1: Vendor managed inventory (VMI) has positive impact on inventory management performance.

Material resource Planning and Inventory Management Performance

The Material Resource Planning (MRP) works with different departments for instance human resource, purchasing, marketing and production thereby aligning them towards a common business strategy (Malhotra et al., 2017). Instead of reacting to reorder quantities the stakeholders are enabled by this system to plan for future product needs (Abdullah & Ambedkar, 2017). Reordering builds on historical use of MRP as per management accounting theory which later evolves into ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) System (Orlicky et al., 1975). MRP systems insights are derived from actual orders and client demand forecasts to prevent costly mistakes, overstock waste or material shortage that affect both cost and profit (Hasbullah et al., 2021; Shao et al., 2021).

Though it was revealed by Clay & Gregg in their study in 1976 that there is a limited view of what the MRP can do since they did not consider machine capacity limitations and fixed lead times. In order to solve these problems finite capacity MRP was introduced by Lunn and Neff in 1992 where variable lead times were incorporated based on processing time, lot size or setup time then developed TOC-MRP for better dealing with capacity issues according Jodlbauer & Reitner (2012). Moreover, Wuttiornpun alongside Yenradee made

some modifications on how capacity limitations should be managed when designing an MRP model during their research work done in 2004.

As Mamani et.al stated, the main purpose of implementing Material Requirement Planning system is to provide timely information about manufacturing or purchased assemblies just before the subsequent stage of production. This has enabled organizations to integrate advanced technologies such as barcodes which help them gain competitive advantage hence highlighting importance of material requirement planning systems in improving inventory management performance. According to a literature review conducted MRPs are still expected to bring about more improvements as far as managing inventory is concerned.H2: Material resource planning system has positive impact on inventory management performance.

Warehouse Management System and Inventory Management Performance

Warehouse operations have been transformed by technology in recent times (Apiyo, & Kiarie, 2018). In the 1990s, warehouses were simply places for storing goods on a large scale, as described by Hayes (2022). Inventory management is crucial to any organization's efficiency according to Panigrahi et al. (2022) who define it as the practice that drives productivity up and cost down through better management of stock levels at various stages among other things. These shifts imply how important warehouse management systems are in today's business landscape where reduced lead time and expense plus capturing customer loyalty cannot be underestimated.

Although many businesses use physical records for their warehousing operations; Xuechun et al. (2007) conducted this research on small enterprises which may not afford such sophisticated systems so they can automate them using information sharing networks that work automatically. This way allows managers to make quicker decisions based on accurate data while avoiding mistakes associated with manual entry methods as pointed out by Sahuri and Putro Utomo (2016). The need for faster processing speeds brought about by shorter product shelf life has necessitated automation of warehousing functions meant to improve throughput rates per hour worked among others like order processing cost reduction according to Sahuri and Putro Utomo (2016).

Kučera et al. (2017) recent case study involved a transportation logistics service provider firm which sought to assess the pros and cons of implementing warehouse management systems within its operations vis-à-vis overall performance improvement along the supply chain. They found out that indeed such an action leads not only to higher satisfaction levels but also lower costs incurred during transportation mainly through route optimization since orders are picked from strategic locations closest possible destinations thereby minimizing distances covered before delivery is made However this was not unique because there were other benefits including controlling storage locations better besides facilitating picking operations which were identified by Giannikas et al. (2013) while looking at challenges faced during adoption of product intelligence paradigm in current systems of warehouse management.

Considering these insights, an automated warehouse management system is imperative for modern warehouses (Atieh, Anas & Kaylani, Hazem & Al Abdallat, Yousef & Qaderi, Abeer & Ghoul, Luma & Jaradat, Lina & Hdairis, Iman, 2016). Such systems control the storage and movement of products, thereby enhancing security levels. Madurapperuma, Ebert, Gamage, and Kuruppuarachchi (2018) developed a Core Brain Warehouse Management System, which assists organizations in optimizing 3rd party logistic (3PL) warehouse operations, ultimately leading to cost reductions and improved inventory performance.

H3: Warehouse management system has positive impact on inventory management performance.

Inventory Management Performance

We aim to address four key factors affecting performance: (1) management of supplier or vendor relationships, (2) optimization of the procurement or ordering process, (3) effective management of sales processes, and (4) customer relationship management. Performance, in this context, encompasses various aspects. SmaËros, Lehtonen, J.-M., Appelqvist, and Holmstro Ëm (2003), examined the integration of traditional order data from non-VMI clients with sales data from VMI clients, assessing its impact on production and inventory control applications. Their findings suggest that inventory control efficiency can be enhanced despite only a partial improvement in demand visibility.

Another study highlighted the three essential components of supply chain management: effective customer management, efficient utilization of organizational resources, and optimal inventory management (Singh & Kumar, 2020). Their research also revealed that the production planning cycle and replenishment frequencies of targeted items significantly influence visibility within the supply chain.

By integrating the supply chain information, supply chain partners can virtually work as a single entity which will enable them together to respond to market's demands. (Khan, S. A., Liang, Y., & Shahzad, S. (2015).). From a financial perspective, inventory management presents a complex challenge as larger inventories incur costs but also offer customers greater purchasing flexibility (Edwin Mongare, & Esther Nasidai, 2014). They suggest that information and communication technology has simplified inventory control systems by facilitating the evaluation of risk factors.

In summary, inventory management significantly influences overall firm performance (Alrjoub, & Ahmad, 2017). Moreover, their research reveals that the cost of capital influences the relationship between inventory management and business performance. They advocate for the adoption of up-to-date ICT tools, including ERP, MRP, RFID, Barcoding, and DRP, to modernize inventory management systems. Such modernization efforts are expected to lead to cost savings and improved profits through waste elimination and reduction of inventory holding costs.

The moderating role of Demand Uncertainty

Product demand mismatches can create a situation where customers are not satisfied, this also leads to market share erosion and increased holding costs. Deneckere, Marve, and Peck (1996) tackle price maintenance with respect to demand uncertainty and discuss the necessary demand conditions required for stock equilibrium. They put forward that at the organizational level there are two strategic approaches to deal with demand uncertainty: shaping and adapting. Shaping involves altering the distribution of demand so as to reduce downside risk while keeping upside potential intact, for example by pricing particular quantities down. On the other hand, adaptation entails aligning operations with different realizations of demands for inventory and profit risks control.

Recently, (S Zhang, Hua, Wang, Zhang, J., & Fernandez, 2018) articulate on two strategies used in minimizing demand uncertainty: probabilistic selling and inventory substitution. Nevertheless, these strategies differ when it comes to operational aspects but they both target on reducing uncertainties of customers' requirements through substituting demands made by encouraging demand which ultimately reduces the impact of demand uncertainty.

H4: Demand uncertainty moderates the relationship between vendor managed inventory and inventory managed performance.

H5: Demand uncertainty moderates the relationship between material resources planning system and inventory management performance.

H6: Demand uncertainty moderates the relationship between warehouse management system and inventory management systems.

Conceptual Model

The conceptual model explicates the correlation between inventory management performance and three pivotal components of information technology systems: Vendor Managed Inventory (VMI) system, Material Demand Planning (MRP) system, and Warehouse Management (WM) system. This model lays the groundwork for subsequent empirical analysis and testing aimed at comprehending the impact of these integrated information technology systems on inventory management performance within practical contexts. Figure 1: Conceptual Model for Inventory Management Performance

Figure 1. Conceptual models constructed by the authors where IT systems are the independent variables.

3. Research Methods

The qualitative research explores into detailed participant experiences, while the survey quantitatively evaluates specific variables. This study adopted a quantitative research approach, employing correlation and regression analysis to investigate the impacts of vendor-managed inventory systems, material requirement planning systems, and warehouse management systems on inventory management effectiveness in selected supermarkets in Oman and Pakistan. Data collection involved gathering cross-sectional data from supply chain managers and supervisors at various time points, primarily post-literature review. Informal interviews with supply chain managers and supervisors were conducted to select the supermarkets, followed by administering personal surveys during their work activities.

A total of 208 usable responses were obtained out of 211 collected from supply chain managers and supervisors of supermarkets in the northeast region. The questionnaire utilized a five-point Likert scale, ranging from "very low extent" to "very great extent," comprising 23 questions related to the effects of the three information technology systems on inventory management performance. Regression analysis was employed to analyze the data, following the conceptual model depicted in Figure 1.

In the first step, a regression model (Equation 1) was estimated to explore the relationships between the information technology systems and inventory management effectiveness:

$$IMP_i = \beta_1 + \beta_2 VMI_i + \beta_3 MRPS_i + \beta_4 + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

Where VMI, MRPS, and WMS represent vendor managed inventory, material demand planning system, and warehouse management system, respectively, serving as independent variables. IMP denotes inventory management performance, the dependent variable. Equation 1 was utilized to test the first three hypotheses.

In the second step, the analysis was extended by incorporating interaction terms to account for demand uncertainty (DU) in Equation 2:

$$IMP_i = \beta_1 + \beta_2 VMI_i + \beta_3 MRPS_i + \beta_4 WMS_i + \beta_5 (VMI_i)(DU_i) + \beta_6 (MRPS_i)(DU_i) + \beta_7 (WMS_i)(DU_i) + \epsilon_i \quad (2)$$

The estimates from β_5 to β_7 facilitated testing of hypotheses 4 to 6. Least squares (NLS and ARMA) were employed to estimate these equations, ensuring none of the assumptions of classical linear equation were violated. The subsequent section presents and discusses the results of the data analysis.

4. Results and Discussion

Demographic profile of the respondents

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the respondents in terms of gender, education level, age category, and work experience. The data shows that the majority of the respondents are male (58.17%) and college graduates with 14 years of education (69.71%). Most respondents fall within the age range of 26 to 40 years (62.98%), and the majority of them have work experience up to five years (65.87%).

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics – Gender and Education

	Number of Respondents	Per cent Responses
Gender		
Female Respondents	87	41.83%
Male Respondents	121	58.17%
Education		
Intermediate	36	17.31%
College Graduate	145	69.71%
16-Years of Education	16	7.69%
More than 16 years of	11	5.29%
	208	100%
Variables Used in the	Mean	Standard Deviation
VMI	3.84	0.84
MRPS	2.58	0.84
WMS	3.98	0.72
DU	3.99	0.75
IMP	3.94	0.58

Correlation Analysis

Table 2. Correlation Analysis

Variables	VMI	MRPS	WMS	DU	IMP
VMI	1				
MRPS	0.27*	1			
WMS	0.64*	0.19*	1		
DU	0.56*	0.33*	0.85*	1	
IMP	0.50*	0.15*	0.77	0.68*	1

Note. VMI, MRPS, WMS, DU and IMP indicate vendor managed inventory, material requirement planning system, warehouse management system, demand uncertainty and inventory management performance respectively. *Significance level is 0.1 (2-tailed). **Insignificant relationship.

Regression analysis and Findings

Moving now to the regression analysis, we applied least squares estimates to Equation 2 and its results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Regression Analysis Inventory Management Performance

Variables	Coefficient	R ²	Adjusted- R ²	P-Value
Step-1				
VMI	0.35			0.000
MRPS	0.10			0.003
WMS	0.61	0.59	0.79	0.000
Stept-2				
VMI*DU	0.11			0.000
MRPS*DU	0.21			0.000
WMS*DU	0.01	0.59	0.66	0.000

Note. VMI, MRPS, WMS, DU and IMP indicate vendor managed inventory, material requirement planning system, warehouse management system, demand uncertainty and inventory management performance respectively.

The regression results in Table 3 provide insights into the relationships between the independent variables (Vendor Managed Inventory, Material Demand Planning, and Warehouse Management) and the dependent variable (Inventory Management Performance). The results show that all three independent variables have a positive and statistically significant impact on the inventory management performance.

Vendor Managed Inventory has a coefficient of 0.35, indicating that an increase in Vendor Managed Inventory leads to a 0.35 unit increase in inventory management performance. Material Demand Planning has a coefficient of 0.10, indicating that an increase in Material Demand Planning leads to a 0.10 unit increase in inventory management performance. Warehouse Management has the highest coefficient of 0.61, indicating that an increase in Warehouse Management leads to a 0.61 unit increase in inventory management performance.

Moreover, the interaction term for Demand Uncertainty moderates the relationships. The coefficient of 0.11 indicates that demand uncertainty strengthens the positive impact of Vendor Managed Inventory, Material Demand Planning, and Warehouse Management on inventory management performance. The R-squared value of 0.59 indicates that the model explains 59% of the variance in inventory management performance, and the Adjusted R-squared value of 0.66 accounts for the model's goodness of fit. Overall, these regression results support all four hypotheses, suggesting that Vendor Managed Inventory, Material Demand Planning, and Warehouse Management positively influence inventory management performance. Additionally, demand uncertainty moderates these relationships, indicating the importance of considering uncertainties in supply chain decision-making.

Based on the analysis of inventory management practices among major supermarkets in Oman and Pakistan, several key findings emerged regarding the impact of demand uncertainty on inventory management performance and the effectiveness of different business models: It emerges from the findings that high demand uncertainty has a strong correlation with stockout or overstock conditions in supermarkets. Target customers in Oman and Pakistan reflected seasonality, macroeconomy, and geography that superstores could not accurately forecast to optimal levels. There was also a problem of uncertainty which led to having to order products in large quantities to ensure that there were safety stocks in case of stockouts. This significantly affected holding cost, efficiency of inventory in the company.

In general, supermarkets operating with a responsive, demand-driven strategy showed better results in inventory management. The features of this model include business intelligence and analytics and demand planning, which would be effective in responding to demands during the course of the season. Employing such models technology enabled supermarkets to reduce its inventory levels, stocked out levels as well as their cost by integrating their current inventory decisions with demand trends. According to the study of (Kumar & Kumar, 2003) computer-based material resource-planning systems are supported by contemporary technology thus facilitating total production plan and monitoring orders right from inception stage up to outputting products at the end of production line. Warehouse management systems which are third control storage as well as movement of materials throughout the channel via different technologies such as barcode

readers or radio-frequency tagging for product tracking (Lysons & Farrington, 2006; Laudon & Laudon, 2015).

Under demand uncertainty, the performance related to inventory management function was found to have been particularly benefited from technology. The research identified a relationship between demand variability and the level of technological resources integrated in supermarkets including demand forecasting software, accurate inventory management systems and point of sale data analysis. Singly, the application of POS and predictive analytics enabled these supermarkets to forecast changes in demand, which in turn enabled these stores to refine their inventory restocking approaches.

Manage demand uncertainty was positively correlated with customer satisfaction because of better stock availability. Other aspects of the modern environment are primarily focused on supermarkets using data analysis to minimize stockouts and provide high product availability to develop customer loyalty. This confirms the proposition that stocking policy should be synchronized with demand variability as a source of competitive edge in the retail industry.

5. Limitations and recommendation for Future Research

The analysis highlights valuable considerations for advancing the study, including limitations and opportunities for future research. Although the current research is focused on supermarkets in Oman and Pakistan, it is important to note that the findings may not be directly transferable to other countries without further investigation and analysis. Variations in cultural, economic, and infrastructural factors across different countries could potentially affect the effectiveness of the variables under study.

As emphasized, remote areas pose unique challenges and requirements in supply chain management. Future research endeavors could explore how the variables studied can be customized or tailored to address the specific needs of such regions, given their limited development and resources.

Developing the scope of research to include different types of businesses other than supermarkets would provide extensive knowledge about how factors under investigation affect inventory management performance across various industries. Accordingly, this could give a wide insight on supply chain optimization strategies for diverse sectors.

Further, there is a possibility that in future research can examine the influence of these studied variables on the cost aspect of inventory management. Examining costs and financial performance implications associated with Vendor Managed Inventory (VMI), material demand planning and warehouse management could be helpful for organizations that want to enhance their supply chain systems.

Additionally, as stated, investigating more aspects concerning information technology such as Distribution Resource Planning within the context of this study may provide a fuller understanding of how various IT components contribute to effectiveness in inventory control.

6. Practical Implications

The results of this research have significant managerial implications for supermarkets in Oman and Pakistan who wish to improve their inventory management performance. The positive and statistically significant effects identified for vendor managed Inventory Systems [VMIS], Material Requirement Planning Systems [MRPS] and Warehouse Management Systems [WMS] are indicative of the key role played by these IT components in strengthening supply chain efficiency.

Similarly, this study shows clearly that demand uncertainty has great impact on inventory management performance. Therefore, through embracing modern technology and encouraging sharing practices supermarkets should be able to respond well to changes in demand thus reduce lead times and increase customer satisfaction by making informed replenishment decisions based on accurate forecast data.

Moreover, our findings indicate that investing in modern technologies is still advantageous even if it comes at some initial costs. This suggests when it comes to improved inventory management; potential cost savings over time can outweigh initial investment.

Based on these findings, therefore it is recommended that retail stores operating in Oman and Pakistan should focus their resources on improving their technological capabilities, communication channels and sharing information among themselves. Concentrating attention here will enable them to realize better outcomes from their supply chains, hence superior performances regarding inventory control.

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, this research has significant implications for further investigation and broadening the scope of the study to give a more comprehensive understanding of inventory management and supply chain optimization in various contexts. Future researchers should address these limitations by considering new perspectives that would advance the practice of supply chain management. Moreover, for Oman and Pakistan supermarkets this is useful research that could be used to improve their inventory management using IT systems as well as managing the uncertainty that comes with demand fluctuations. The listed recommendations have potential ramifications in terms of improved effectiveness of supply chain management leading to better performance of firms and heightened customer satisfaction levels.

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